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PRACTICAL NOTE BOOK

Botany

Roll: 2200147461, Course code: MPCL-07
Name: KHRISHNA SWARHARY
MAPL, 1st Year, IGNOU, RC-18 Midlong.
Class Roll Year 2022-23

Master's Degree Programme in Psychology

**HANDBOOK ON PRACTICUM
EXPERIMENTAL PSYCHOLOGY AND
PSYCHOLOGICAL TESTING (MPCL-007)**

**Discipline of Psychology
School of Social Sciences
Indira Gandhi National Open University
Maidan Garhi, New Delhi- 110068**

**TITLE PAGE FOR PRACTICUM NOTEBOOK
IGNOU
MA (PSYCHOLOGY)**

Programme Code: MAPC

Course Code: MPCL-007

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Regional Centre: 18, Shillong.

Date: 26/03/2023

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Name : KHRITISH SWARGIARY

Father's Name :

Address :

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Signature
Student Registered in District

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Ms/ Mr. Khrish Swargary
of MA Psychology First Year has conducted and successfully completed the practical work in
MPCL- 007 Practicum: Experimental Psychology and Psychological Testing.

Khrish Swargary
Signature of the Learner

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Enrolment No.: 22 00147461

Name of the Study Centre:

Regional Centre: 18, Shillong.

Place: Shillong.

Date: 26-03-2023

Wandahan Swargary
Signature of Academic Counsellor

Name: Wandahan Swargary

Designation: Clinical Psychologist

Place: Shillong

Date: 26.3.23

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This is to acknowledge that Ms./Mr. Khrish Swarjany.....
Enrollment No. 2200147461..... of MAPC (1st Year) has submitted the
Practicum Notebook at the study centre 180/1863....., Regional
Centre 18, Shillong.....

Date: 26/03/23

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(Coordinator, Study Centre)

CO - ORDINATOR
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SAN - KER Academic and Research Centre
Mawroh Shillong - 793008
Meghalaya

Expt. No.

Page No.

Date.

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EXPERIMENT NO: 1Title: Family Pathology Scale.Participant's details:

Name - KS

Age - 29

Sex - Male

Religion - Hinduism

Caste - ST

Type of family - Nuclear

Siblings - 1

Educational level of father - 10th Pass

Business of father - Agriculture

Income of father - 60,000/- INR

Residential Address - Bangeigam, Arnam.

Introduction:

The family is a primary social unit of every culture. In India, the family rather than the individual has been considered as the unit of social system. The Indian family reflects the socio-cultural fabric of Indian society, its philosophy and values (Sethi, 1989).

The relationships within a family are complex of varying degrees of intensity and myriad in nature. The emotion tone, which governs the relationship between any two persons, is continuously influenced in its course by emotional relationships of all others in the family. This changing manifold emotional currents and cross-currents determines the prevailing "atmosphere" in the family which sets the basis for interaction and interpersonal relationships in the family.

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The family is of central importance to human beings and it is inconceivable

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to think of an individual's development without a family. The biological, sociological and socio-cultural functions of the family occur in terms of the interactions of the family members with each other and with other persons outside of the family. These interactions are the basic foundations over which the edifices of the family are built up. Over the centuries the many social changes that have occurred in societies have in one way or the other affected these interactions, yet despite these changes in the family has retained its unity and identity more or less in the same way as in the past with very little change.

This is all the more so in India. As is well known, in Indian setting the joint family system to an extent, has given way to nuclear family system and in a few cases, to single parent families, as is obtained in the western world, yet one cannot deny the fact

the child and the parents are part of a family. The strong emotional bond which exist among the members of a family, the typical roles and functions of each member, the values, the cultural influence, the religious affinity and the social mores play a significant role in the development of the personality of an individual born in the family.

In India, even today, the influence of the family of an individual's life is very high in that there is still relatively lesser scope for individual decision-making vis a vis family decision-making. The interactions continue to be relatively more one sided viz, parent to the child, the husband to the wife and the grand parent to the parent. This could be seen in many families, where one finds practically an inflexible interaction of a one sided nature.

In western families, while children become independent of the parents by the time they finish the school, in India, the dependence of an individual on his family continues on. While the core relationship in the western families hinges between the husband and wife, in India it rests between the parent and the child.

Sethi (1989), describes Indian families as having lasting roots in the past generation extending on to future generation almost making one full cycle.

Development of the scale:

The family pathology scale, indicate the extent to which maladaptive behaviour is present amongst the family members in their interaction with each other i.e. between spouses and between parents and children. A total of 100 items were prepared in the form of statements which had to be rated on a 3-point scale, with 1 indicating 'low/no family

pathology ('Never' response), 2 indicating 'average family pathology' ('occasional' response) and 3 indicating 'high family pathology' ('most often' response).

The scale consisting of 100 items was distributed to 25 clinical psychologists and 25 psychiatrists. The judges were asked to indicate as to what extent each item was indicative of family pathology on a three-point scale, i.e. "highly indicative", "somewhat indicative" and "not at all indicative". Using the internal consistency method, only those items were chosen on which the rating was the same amongst all the 50 experts. Secondly, the items, which were given a rating of 1 indicating poor family pathology, differed by two points from the item that was chosen as indicative of high family pathology. Only those items were selected and included in the final scale for family pathology, which met the above two criteria.

Thus, there are 42 items in the scale to be responded by the subjects with 'most often', 'occasionally' and 'never'. These were then administered to a group of 300 married couples from the normal population, ($N=600$) and 100 couples from the psychiatric (pathological) population ($N=200$) and the reliability and validity were worked out.

Administration:

This is a self-administered scale. The respondents are given the instruction to complete all the statements by making a tick on any of the three responses 'most often' , 'occasionally' or 'never' whichever is applicable in their case.

They were asked not to omit any item from the scale. It was emphasized that there was nothing 'right' or 'wrong' about these items and they should answer all items frankly and truthfully without

inhibition. Since many items were highly personal to the individuals, they were assured of confidentiality of their responses. Both husband and wife were asked to independently rate each scale.

Scoring : Items indicative of 'high family pathology' were given 3 by ticking 'most often', 'moderate family pathology' given 2 points by ticking on 'occasionally' and 'no family pathology' was assigned a score of 1 by ticking 'never' response. Total score possible to obtain ranged between 42-126 with higher score indicating higher family pathology, and lower score indicating the reverse.

Interpretation : All the 42 items selected were indicative of family pathology. There were to be tick - marked by the respondents as what extent the behaviour occurred 'most often', 'occasionally' and

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[Faint, illegible handwritten text in the middle section]

[Faint, illegible handwritten text at the bottom of the page]

'never'. Where the response occurred 'most often', it was indicative of high family pathology, while 'occasionally' and 'never' were indicative of average and no family pathology at all respectively. These scores were classified into three categories based on the scores obtained by the normal population ($N = 600$) and the pathological population ($N = 200$). The categories are as follows:

Low / No pathology	42 - 63
Moderate Pathology	64 - 98
High Pathology	99 - 128

On a continuum running from 42 to 128, the 3 categories will fall at the points indicated.

High family pathology is indicated in the 98-128 area and moderate family pathology being between 64-98. The scores below 64 are indicative of low or without pathology.

This means and standard deviations for the normal and pathology population are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1.

Groups	Mean	Standard deviation	N
Normal Population	48.6	7.60	600
Psychiatric Population	96.8	8.70	200

Reliability:

(i) The split-half reliability correlation odd-even items applying Spearman Brown formula for doubling the test length was found to be $X_{tt} = .57$, $N = 600$ within an index of reliability of $X_{tt} = .70$.

(ii) The test-retest reliability for this scale was $X_{tt} = 0.79$.

The test-retest reliability was estimated to be $X_{tt} = 0.633$, with an index of reliability $X_{tt} = .79$. These are presented in Table 2 below.

TABLE 2.

Split-half and test-retest reliability values

	N	Index of reliability
Split-half	600	.70
Test-retest	600	.79

Validity :

(i) The face validity of the questionnaire appeared to be fairly high, as items were prepared following intensive interviews of 300 couples regarding the extent of family pathology present in the family.

(ii) The content validity was adequately assured as only those items were selected for the initial scale for which there was complete agreement amongst the experts.

Scoring table and Interpretation :

	Raw Score			Interpretation
	2	3	4	
Page	2	3	4	Low family Pathology
Score	23	21	16	
Total Score	60			

Conclusion : Subject has low family pathology, hence no requirement of family counselling.

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Consumable Booklet
of

FPS-VVDA
(English Version)

Dr. Vimala Veeraraghavan (New Delhi)
Dr. Archana Dogra (New Delhi)

Please fill up the following informations :

Dated

1 7 0 3 2 0 2 3

Name A

Sex : Male

Caste

Religion Hindu

Type of Family

No.

Educational level of Father

mother

Business of Father A

mother

Income of Father 6

Mother

Residential Address

INSTRUCTIONS

In this booklet, 42 statements are given which depict the behaviour of an individual in the family surroundings and his perception towards family members. You have to read each statement carefully and mark the tick on any of the three response mode against each statement. Example : Most often Occassionally Never

I think that my family members have sympathy for me.

As occasionally is true in this case, tick is marked in the cell below occasionally. In this way each response is to be given.

Scoring Table

Page	Raw Score			Interpretation
	2	3	4	
Score	23	21	16	Low Pathology
Total Score	60			

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Most often - 3
 occasionally - 2
 Never - 1

2 | Consumable Booklet of FPS-WDA

Sr. No.	STATEMENTS	Most Often	Occasionally	Never	SCORE
1.	I ask the child to come. The moment he comes, I send him back. I can never say what I want to communicate.	☐	☐	☒	1
2.	I am all the time on guard, lest what I say may make the other person hurt me.	☐	☐	☒	1
3.	I am always worried about what other family members think about me and my behaviour.	☒	☐	☐	3
4.	I always fear that my children may leave me.	☐	☐	☒	1
5.	In my house, quarrels are invariably among the members not following certain rules and regulations.	☐	☒	☐	2
6.	I spend hours together on prayers and insist that others should also do the same.	☒	☒	☐	2
7.	I have to spend hours together in wiping, cleaning and dusting.	☒	☐	☐	3
8.	I have to wash everything because I feel my family members have defiled the things since they did not wash themselves.	☐	☐	☒	1
9.	I sometimes feel that I spend all my time on all these activities and have no time to rest.	☐	☐	☒	1
10.	I keep testing every now and then whether the children love me or not.	☐	☒	☐	2
11.	I always want the children to come to me and demonstrate their affection.	☐	☒	☐	2
12.	I get panicky when they (children) show more affection towards an outsider lest they get attracted towards them.	☐	☐	☒	1
13.	I get angry when the children spend more time with my spouse than me.	☐	☐	☒	1
14.	I like to see my children always around me.	☐	☒	☐	2
Total Score Page No. 2					23

Consumable Booklet of FPS-WDA | 3

Sr. No.	STATEMENTS	Most Often	Occasionally	Never	SCORE
15.	I never send them to the relatives or friends house even for a few hours.	☐	☐	☒	1
16.	I feel very nervous when the child expresses a wish to go away from home.	☐	☐	☒	1
17.	I keep telling my child he should do things as I say.	☐	☒	☐	2
18.	I keep rewarding my child for everything but still I find he/she is not attached to me.	☐	☒	☐	2
19.	Over the years my rewarding techniques have become more and more expensive for me.	☐	☐	☒	1
20.	I get hurt when the child disobeys me.	☐	☒	☐	2
21.	Whenever I get angry or frustrated, I punish the child.	☐	☐	☒	1
22.	I feel so disturbed by the children that I lock them in the room for atleast 3-4 hours a day.	☐	☐	☒	1
23.	Sometimes my anger becomes so extreme that I just don't know what I am doing to the child, later I regret my action and cry over it.	☐	☐	☒	1
24.	I keep apologizing to the child whenever I think he's angry with me.	☐	☐	☒	1
25.	I am constantly in tension that my family members may mistake me.	☐	☒	☐	2
26.	I keep trying to please everyone in the family and in the process I find I have no time for myself.	☐	☒	☐	2
27.	I feel very happy that my family is totally dependent on me.	☐	☐	☒	1
28.	If any family member talks well of any other family member I get completely put off.	☐	☐	☒	1
29.	I want everyone in the family to appreciate me, reassure me that I am on the right path.	☐	☒	☐	2
Total Score Page No. 3					21

Sr. No.	STATEMENTS	Most Often	Occasionally	Never	SCORE
30.	I insist on everyone to be perfect.	☐	☐	☒	1
31.	I just cannot tolerate even a small deflection from perfection.	☐	☒	☐	2
32.	I get easily put off when the child obeys others and not me.	☐	☐	☒	1
33.	If the child does not return from school on time, I get panicky.	☐	☐	☒	1
34.	I insist on accompanying my child to every place he/she goes to despite his/her protest.	☐	☐	☒	1
35.	The moment the child leaves home, I start visualizing and imaging that some bad incident has occurred and get totally panicky.	☐	☐	☒	1
36.	I insist that the child should ring me up when he / she reaches their destination and ring me back when they start to leave.	☐	☒	☐	2
37.	I can never let my child go to a hostel.	☐	☐	☒	1
38.	When the child misses his food even a little bit, I get very worried.	☐	☒	☐	2
39.	I sometimes try to win the child by crying.	☐	☐	☒	1
40.	I keep telling the child how great I am, how grateful he should be towards me for all I have done.	☐	☐	☒	1
41.	I insist on proper loving behaviour on the part of the child for all I have done for him.	☐	☐	☒	1
42.	When I go to work or anywhere outside, my mind is always back home with the children and I just cannot enjoy the shopping etc.	☐	☐	☒	1

Total Score Page No. 4 16

Sr. No.	STATEMENTS	Most Often	Occasionally	Never	SCORE
30.	I insist on everyone to be perfect.	☐	☐	☒	1
31.	I just cannot tolerate even a small deflection from perfection.	☐	☒	☐	2
32.	I get easily put off when the child obeys others and not me.	☐	☐	☒	1
33.	If the child does not return from school on time, I get panicky.	☐	☐	☒	1
34.	I insist on accompanying my child to every place he/she goes to despite his/her protest.	☐	☐	☒	1
35.	The moment the child leaves home, I start visualizing and imaging that some bad incident has occurred and get totally panicky.	☐	☐	☒	1
36.	I insist that the child should ring me up when he / she reaches their destination and ring me back when they start to leave.	☐	☒	☐	2
37.	I can never let my child go to a hostel.	☐	☐	☒	1
38.	When the child misses his food even a little bit, I get very worried.	☐	☒	☐	2
39.	I sometimes try to win the child by crying.	☐	☐	☒	1
40.	I keep telling the child how great I am, how grateful he should be towards me for all I have done.	☐	☐	☒	1
41.	I insist on proper loving behaviour on the part of the child for all I have done for him.	☐	☐	☒	1
42.	When I go to work or anywhere outside, my mind is always back home with the children and I just cannot enjoy the shopping etc.	☐	☐	☒	1

Total Score Page No. 4 16

EXPERIMENT NO. : 2Title : Problem Behaviour Checklist.Problem : To measure or identify the emotional and conduct problems of the child.Participant's details :

Name - K B

Age - 16

Sex - Male

Religion - Christian

Type of family - Nuclear

No. of siblings - 1

Caste - ST

Educational level of father - 10th pass.

Business of father - Agriculture.

Income of father - 60,000/- INR

Residential Address - Bongaigaon, Assam.

Introduction :

Emotional and behavioural disorders are common in childhood and adolescence.

The special features of children's psychiatric problems are that the disturbance in the child may result from problems in other members of the family, especially the parents. Another aspect is whether the behaviour, which is considered abnormal, is related to the child's stage of development. There are many types of disorders, which may have common symptoms. Since the child depends on a great deal on the family, especially on the mother for a stable, secure family environment which facilitates emotional bond, acceptance and consistent discipline, a lack in any of these aspects may predispose the child to emotional and conduct disorders. While assessment of the problems in childhood is basically carried out by interviewing the parents, often one finds a checklist helpful to make a clear-cut diagnosis as pointed out by Holland and Kendall

(1980), Burgess (1990) and Schmidt et al. (1985). The most common assessment strategy is the self report questionnaire, which are designed to represent dysfunction in different areas of behaviour. Higher scores on such questionnaires indicate that the individual endorses more items reflecting the type of cognition and behaviour the scale measured. Higher levels of endorsement correlate with measures of psychopathology. The literature in this regard is filled with construct specific scales and their relation to certain types of psychopathology (Linscott and Di Giuseppe, 1989).

Several behaviour problem checklists in which parents are asked to rate their child's behaviours have been developed and extensively studied. For example, one such checklist is "Child Behaviour Checklist" (CBCL), by Achenbach and Edelbrock (1983). In behaviour problem checklist, a child is characterised in terms of his or her position along

each possible behavioural dimension as compared to children in the normal population.

Development of the Checklist :

The checklist was devised to identify the emotional and conduct problems of children. The following procedure was adopted for developing this scale.

A total of 100 items was prepared in the form of symptoms which had to be related on a three point scale, with 1, 2 and 3 indicative of 'no', 'average' and 'high' problem behaviour. As per ICD-10 specific diagnostic criteria were included separately for emotional, conduct and mixed disorders of conduct and emotions.

These 100 items were then given to 25 psychologists and 25 psychiatrists.

Using the internal consistency method, only those items were chosen on which

the rating was the same amongst all the 50 experts. Using the principles, 58 items were selected from a total of 100 items.

Thus, there are 58 items in the scale to be responded by the Parent's with 'most often', 'occasionally' and 'never'. These were then administered to a group of 300 couples from the normal population, (N = 600) and 100 couples from the psychiatric (pathological) population (N = 200) and the reliability and validity were worked out.

Administration : These items were to be tick - marked by the parents as to whether the symptoms occurred 'most often', 'occasionally' or 'never'. Where the response occurred 'most often', it was indicative of high problem behaviour and 'occasionally' and 'never' were indicative of 'average' and 'no problem behaviour', respectively.

Scoring : Items indicative of 'high problem behaviour' were given 3, 'average' and 'no problem behaviour' were assigned a score of 2 and 1 respectively. Total scores obtained ranged between 58-174, thus indicating that the higher the score, the higher the problem behaviour of the child, and the lower the score, the lower problem behaviour of the child.

Interpretation : All the 58 items selected were indicative of behaviour problem in children. These were to be tick-marked by the respondents on a 1-3 point scale, as to what extent the behaviour occurred 'most often', 'occasionally' and 'never'. Thus the scores range between 58 and 174. These scores were divided into three categories based on the scores obtained by the normal population ($N = 600$) and the pathological population ($N = 200$). These categories are as follows :

Low problem behaviour	- 58 - 96.
Moderate problem behaviour	- 97 - 135.
High problem behaviour	- 136 - 174.

In a scale running from 58-174, the rating low, moderate and high will fall on the continuum as given in the figure 1.

The mean and standard deviation for behaviour problem scores for the normal population of $N = 600$ and parents with manifesting problem behaviour $N = 200$ were worked out.

The tables below presents the details.

TABLE 1

Groups	Mean	Standard Deviation	N
Normal Population	57.38	8.42	600
Psychiatric population	158.78	6.88	200

Reliability :

(i) The test-retest reliability for this scale was $X_n = .85$, with an index of reliability was 0.85.

(ii) The split-half reliability correlating odd even items applying Spearman Brown formula for doubling the test length was found to be $X_n = .72$, $N = 600$, with an index of reliability $r_n = .81$.

There are presented in Table 2.

Split-half and test-retest reliability values.		
	N	Index of reliability
Split half	600	.81
Test-retest	600	.85

Validity :

(i) The face validity of the questionnaire appeared to be fairly high as the

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items were prepared following intensive interviews with 300 couples regarding the extent of problem behaviour in their children as perceived by them.

(ii) The content validity was adequately assured as only those items were selected for the initial questionnaire for which there was complete agreement amongst the experts.

Finally, those items which showed a high discriminating value following item analysis were selected for the final test. The diagnostic meaningfulness of the items at the time of final selection was also taken into consideration.

Data analysis of scoring table :

	Raw Score			Interpretation
Page	2	3	4	
Score	41	13	23	Low Problem
Total score	77			behaviour.

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Expt. No.

Page No. 43

Date.

Conclusion: As we observed that total score is 77 which indicates 'Low problem behaviour, hence requires no consultancy or counsellor.

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Dr. Vimala Veeraraghavan (New Delhi)
Dr. Archana Dogra (New Delhi)

Consumable Booklet

of

P B C L - V D

(English Version)

Please fill up the following Informations : Date

2 2 0 3 2 0 2 3

Name of the Child _____

Sex : Male _____

Type of Family _____

Educational level of Father _____ Mother _____

Business of Father _____ Mother _____

Income of Father 60 _____ Mother _____

Residential Address _____

Instructions

(This Checklist is to be filled by parents of the children.)

In this booklet, 58 behavioural problems are listed for three response categories, the parents have to assess degree of the problems which are related to their children. He has to read each problem one by one and assess whether that problem occurs **Most often** , **Occasionally** or **Never** in the case of the child in question. He has to give his response by marking tick against the cell below that response mode.

SCORING TABLE

Page	Raw Score			Interpretation
	2	3	4	
Score	41	13	23	low Problem behaviour
Total Score	77			

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Sr. No.	STATEMENTS	Most Often	Occasionally	Never	Score
Does your Child have :—					
1.	Fear of animals ?	☐	☒	☐	2
2.	Nail biting problems ?	☐	☒	☐	2
3.	Thumb sucking tendency ?	☐	☒	☐	2
4.	Involuntary wetting of the bed ?	☐	☒	☐	2
5.	Involuntary soiling of pants ?	☐	☒	☐	2
6.	Disturbed sleep ?	☐	☐	☒	1
7.	Increase in temper tantrums ?	☐	☒	☐	2
8.	Social withdrawal tendency ?	☐	☒	☐	2
9.	Tendency to babyish behaviour.	☐	☒	☐	2
10.	Increased Irritability ?	☐	☒	☐	2
11.	Speech characterized by frequent repetition / prolongation of sounds or syllabus or words (stammering) ?	☐	☒	☐	2
12.	Scholastic problems ?	☐	☐	☒	1
13.	Anxiety ?	☐	☐	☒	1
14.	Speech articulation defect ?	☐	☐	☒	1
15.	Examination phobia ?	☐	☒	☐	2
16.	Poor memory ?	☐	☒	☐	2
17.	Lack of attention ?	☐	☒	☐	2
18.	Lack of concentration ?	☐	☒	☐	2
19.	Fussy eating habits ?	☐	☒	☐	2
20.	Regression of Previously acquired skills (such as bowel & bladder control) ?	☐	☐	☒	1
21.	Strong reluctance to share with sibling ?	☐	☐	☒	1
22.	Lack of positive regard for sibling ?	☐	☐	☒	1
23.	Few friendly Interactions with sibling(s) ?	☐	☐	☒	1
24.	Hostility, physical trauma and/ or maliciousness towards sibling ?	☐	☐	☒	1
25.	Undermining tendencies towards the sibling ?	☐	☐	☒	1
26.	Marked competition with siblings for the attention with an unusual degree of negative feelings ?	☐	☐	☒	1

Total Score 41

Sr. No.	STATEMENTS	Most Often	Occasionally	Never	Score
27.	Persistent or recurrent fear/avoidance of strangers and peers ?	☐	☐	☒	1
28.	Unrealistic, preoccupying worry that some untoward event such as the child being lost, kidnapped, admitted to hospital or killed, will separate him/her from mother/father/grand parent/any other ?	☐	☐	☒	1
29.	Unrealistic worry about possible harm befalling the attachment figure or a fear that they will leave and not return ?	☐	☐	☒	1
30.	Persistent reluctance/refusal to go to school because of fear of separation ?	☐	☒	☐	2
31.	Persistent reluctance/refusal to go to sleep without being near to the attachment figure ?	☐	☒	☐	2
32.	Persistent inappropriate fear of being alone or without parent the whole day ?	☐	☒	☐	2
33.	Repeated nightmares about separation ?	☐	☐	☒	1
34.	Repeated occurrence of physical symptoms (Nausea, stomach ache, headache, vomiting) on occasions that involve separation such as leaving home to go to the school ?	☐	☐	☒	1
35.	Excessive recurrent distress (crying, tantrums, social withdrawal) in anticipation or during or immediately following separation from the attachment figure ?	☐	☐	☒	1
36.	Self-injurious behaviour ?	☐	☐	☒	1
37.	Persistent and marked depression of mood ; Excessive misery, Loss of interest and pleasure in usually enjoyable activities, Self-blame, Hopelessness ?	☐	☐	☒	1

Total Score

13

Sr. No.	STATEMENTS	Most Often	Occasionally	Never	Score
38.	Aggressive behaviour ?	☐	☒	☐	0
39.	Defiant conduct ?	☐	☐	☒	0
40.	Excessive levels of fighting/bullying ?	☐	☐	☒	0
41.	Cruelty to animals or other people ?	☐	☐	☒	0
42.	Severe destructiveness to property ?	☐	☐	☒	0
43.	Fire setting habits ?	☐	☐	☒	0
44.	Stealing habits ?	☐	☐	☒	0
45.	Repeated lying habits ?	☐	☐	☒	0
46.	Habit of truancy from school ?	☐	☐	☒	0
47.	Habit of running away from home ?	☐	☐	☒	0
48.	Habit of unusual frequent temper tantrums ?	☐	☐	☒	0
49.	Defiant provocative behaviour.	☐	☐	☒	0
50.	Persistent severe disobedience ?	☐	☐	☒	0
51.	Isolation from and/or rejection by or unpopularity with other children ?	☐	☐	☒	0
52.	Lack of close friends ?	☐	☒	☐	0
53.	Hostile relations with adults ?	☐	☐	☒	0
54.	Resistance to authority ?	☐	☐	☒	0
55.	Deliberate attempts to annoy others ?	☐	☐	☒	0
56.	Annoying tendencies on trivial incidents.	☐	☐	☒	0
57.	Blaming tendencies towards others for his mistakes/ difficulties.	☐	☐	☒	0
58.	Violation of age appropriate social expectations in terms of manners, academic performance and compliance with adults, rules and regulations ?	☐	☐	☒	0

Total Score 23

EXPERIMENT NO.: 3

Title : Span of Immediate Memory
(visual and Auditory).

Problem : How many numbers can be reproduced after getting only one exposure auditorily?

Hypothesis : After one exposure only 7 ± 2 figures can be reproduced.

Variables : Independent variable - The number of numerals presented to the subject.
Dependent variable - The maximum number recalled by the subject.

Materials and Apparatus :

1. Three lists of numerals ranging from 3 to 12.
2. Screen.
3. Paper and Pencil.

Introduction : To bring any past experience as it is to present consciousness is known as memory.

The memorizing process or memory may be of two types - (i) immediate memory i.e. to recall some experience immediately after its occurrence, without any time lapse. (ii) Permanent memory i.e. to recall any experience or task after hours or years.

Immediate memory may be of two types (i) Visual and (ii) Auditory.

(i) In experiments related to visual memory the stimulus material is presented visually and subject recall is writing, in such experiments the mental images are also visual.

(ii) In Auditory memory experiments the stimulus material is presented auditory either verbally or through tape recorders. The subject also produces the material verbally.

The amount of material reproduced immediately after one exposure is respectively known as auditory or visual span of immediate memory.

Individual differences are found in memory span. It is affected by the nature of material, (abstract, concrete, familiar rare) length and method of presentation, subject's interest, motivation, intelligence, age, etc.

Jacobs (1887) was the first to conduct a simple experiment to demonstrate the immediate memory span. The span for meaningful words are more than the non sense syllables.

Practice also affect the memory span. According to, Bell's telephonic laboratory the span for numerals is always more than the letters or words. It is for this reason that numerals are used for telephones and vehicles.

The memory span is also affected by the age of the individual. The maximum

Span is at the age of 25 years after this it decreases to some extent. The increase in span is slower up to the age of 13-years, it increases rapidly between 13-16 years and the maximum increase takes place between 22 to 25 years.

The memory span is 4 at the age of 4 to 5 years, 5 between the age of 6 to 8 years, 6 between the age range of 8 to 12 years and 9 at the age of 12 years.

According to Guildford, the memory span of an average individual is 7. But the magic number of 7 ± 2 is provided by Muller, which is broadly accepted.

Immediate memory process, depends on mental activity of preservation. The effect of any stimulus experiences, do not perish immediately but its after effect persists for less or more time in consciousness, eg. visual and auditory after images.

Experimental Precautions :

1. Subject was seated comfortably and its calm and quite atmosphere.
2. While preparing the list care was taken not to write numbers in any organized way i.e. serially, reverse order or odd or even numbers.
3. While presenting the number strings to the subjects, care should be taken not to present the numeral in any cluster form e.g. 59, 729, etc. but each number should be presented as a unit. e.g., 205 as two, zero and five.
In each trial, the pronunciation and should be kept constant.
4. The list should not be shown to the subject.

Participant's Profile :

Name - BS

Age - 33

Date of Birth - 06/05/1990

Rural / Urban - Urban

Qualification - M.A

Address - Gowahati, Assam.

Instructions : After getting subject being seated comfortably the following instructions were given.

"The success of the experiment depends on your cooperation and attention, therefore kindly be attentive to the instructions I am giving you".

I will give you the 'ready' and 'listen' signals. As soon as I give you the signal of 'listen', I will produce some numbers. You listen them attentively. These numbers will be spoken only once. You have to repeat them in same sequence immediately after

listening them. The beginning of the numbers which will be increased gradually upto ten numbers.

If any thing is not clear to you, ask it without any hesitation.

Procedure and Administration:

After explaining the instructions to the subject, the experiment properly was started.

The subject was produced a three number string from the list after giving her the signal of listen. After presenting the number string, she was asked to repeat. The reproduction of string was noted down in the similar form as produced by the subject.

The same procedure was repeated with each string of the list, till the subject failed to reproduce the string correctly. The numbers of last correctly reproduce string was counted and noted down.

The same procedure was repeated with other two lists.

Results and Observations :Statistical Observations

List No.	Stimulating list	Response list	Span of memory
First	827	827	8
	5182	5182	
	79582	79592	
	869541	869541	
	3852673	3852673	
	49158216	4158216	
	928637514		
Second	561	561	8
	8527	8527	
	34916	34916	
	665847	665847	
	2597418	2597418	
	72853641	72853641	
	495713628		
Third	957	957	7
	5294	5294	
	69738	69738	

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738259	738259	
3958627	3958627	
83792415		

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The average auditory memory span} &= \frac{\sum X}{N} \\ &= \frac{23}{3} \\ &= 7.66 \end{aligned}$$

Interpret

($\sum X$ = The total correct number of last string produced by the subject from each list; $N = 3$)

Conclusion :

The average number of reproduction is the immediate auditory memory span of the subject.

Title : Immediate visual memory span.

Problem : How many letters can be reproduced after getting only one exposure visually?

Hypothesis : After one exposure only 7 ± 2 letters can be reproduced.

Variables :

Independent - The two separate sets of 3 stimulus list each for two subjects.

Dependent - The number of letters reproduced by the subjects.

Materials and Apparatus :

1. Three lists each of nine letters arranged in different form.
2. Screen.

Precautions : While preparing the lists, precautions was kept that (a) the letters were written at proper distance and by dark ink.

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- (b) No meaningful relationships exists between the letters of the list.
- (c) The organization of letters for different lists were kept different.
- (d) equal number of letters were kept in each list.

Lists were not shown to the subjects before the start of experiment proper. Each list was shown to the subject only for 15 seconds. After the presentation of each list a rest of 30 seconds was given to the subject.

Instructions: The subject was seated comfortably and the following instructions were given.

The success of the experiment depends on your cooperation and attention, therefore kindly be attentive and listen the instruction.

I will give the 'ready' and 'see' signals immediately after giving you the 'see'

signal. I will produce a list of letters before you.

Kindly keep your eyes at the centre letter of the list and try to remember different letters of the list.

After a brief duration, I will remove the list. The list will be shown only once. After the removal of list, you will be given a paper on which you have to write the letters you have seen in the list in the same order.

You have to do the same task with different lists in which the organization of letters will be different.

If there is anything which is not clear to you then please ask about it.

Procedure : After making sure that the subject have understood the instructions, the experiment proper was started.

After giving the 'ready' and 'see' signals the first list was presented to the subject for 15 seconds and then the list was removed and a paper was given to the subject with the instruction to write the letters of the list in the same form. In this way, all the three lists were presented to the subject. A 30 seconds inter list presentation interval was kept.

Analysis and Scoring :

The subject was given a weightage of two for writing a letter at correct place and order, one for writing correct letter at wrong place or order. No mark were given for writing a wrong letter. While scoring the list attention was paid to the following errors ;

- (1) Mistake of Transposition, e.g. writing MAR in place of MRA.
- (2) Mistake of Omission e.g. writing MR in place of MRA.
- (3) Mistake of commission, e.g. writing MRA X in place of MRA.
- (4) Mistake of Transposition and Commission, e.g. writing MAT.

Statistical Observation:

List No.	Stimulating list	Response list	Span of Memory	Total obtained
First	X P T	X P T	2 2	14
	M M F	M M F	2 2 2	
	D A	D	2 2	
	R	R		
Second	C N F	C N F	2 2 2	18
	U R	U R L	2 2 2	
	E L	E A	2 2	
	T K	T	2 0	

Third	D S A	D S A	2 2 2	
	S P L	S P L	2 2 2	16
	R	R K	2	
	G P	G	2	

$$\text{Total} = 14 + 18 + 16 = 48$$

$$\text{Mean} = \frac{\sum x}{N} = \frac{48}{3} = 16$$

Interpretation and Conclusion!

On the basis of analysis and conclusions are drawn and data is interpreted i.e. 16 is the immediate memory span of the subject.

T. M. Regd. No. 564838
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Dr. Rakhi Bhargava (Lucknow)
Abha Bhargava (Udaipur)

Consumable Booklet
of

SIM-BB

(Visual & Auditory)
(English/Hindi Version)

Fill in the Informations (निम्न सूचनाएँ भरिए) – Date (दिनांक)

17	03	19	90
----	----	----	----

Name (नाम) _____

Age (आयु) _____

Date of Birth (जन्म-तिथि) 01 / 01 / 1990 – Rural/Urban (ग्रामाण/शहरी) _____

Qualifications (योग्यताएँ) _____

Address (पता) _____

INSTRUCTIONS

1. In the starting the experiment, "ready" is called for the purpose of being ready for experiment.
2. Immediately after "Ready" indication of "see" will be given and a list of alphabets is presented in front of you.
3. Concentrate your sight on the middle alphabet of the list and try to see the different alphabets and their position also try to remember them.
4. The presented alphabet list shall be removed soon indicating by "that is all". So pay your attention properly on the experimental list.
5. Experimental list will be shown to you only once.

निर्देश

1. 'सावधान' का संकेत सुनते ही ध्यानपूर्वक सुनने के लिए तैयार हो जाइये।
2. 'सावधान' संकेत के तुरन्त बाद मैं आपके सामने कुछ अंक तथा अक्षर बोलूँगा।
3. आप ध्यानपूर्वक सुनिष्ठा तथा मेरे बोले गए अंक अक्षरों को उसी क्रम में दुहराएँगे।
4. अंक तथा अक्षरों को मैं दूसरी बार नहीं बोलूँगा, अतः ध्यानपूर्वक सुनें तथा मेरे द्वारा बोले गए अक्षरों तथा अंकों को उसी क्रम में दुहराएँ।

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Part I : Visual (दृश्यात्मक)

Subject was shown the following first, second and third list for 15 seconds each consecutively. Answer of each trial was noted on separate paper.

प्रयोज्य को क्रमिक रूप से प्रत्येक प्रयास में 15-15 सेकण्ड के लिए (अलग-अलग कार्ड पर अंकित) प्रथम, द्वितीय व तृतीय सूची (केवल तीन, हिन्दी अथवा अंग्रेजी की) दिखलाई गई। प्रयोज्य का प्रत्युत्तर, प्रत्येक प्रयास में अलग-अलग कागज पर अंकित कराया गया।

List No. सूची संख्या	Stimulating List उद्दीपक सूची						Response List प्रत्युत्तर-सूची	Span of Memory मूल्यांकन	Total Obtained प्राप्तांक-योग
I First प्रथम	X M	P M D R	T K A	म ल	ट फ ब य	ह क ग	X P T M M T D R K	2 2 2 2 2 2 2 0	14
II Second द्वितीय	C U	N R E T	F L K	य ट अ	र न च	छ क द	C N F U R T L	2 2 2 2 2 2 2 2 0	18
III Third तृतीय	D S	S P R G	A L P	स ड	ब फ द म	च ह ख	D S A S P L S P L	2 2 2 2 2 2 2 2 0	16
IV Fourth चतुर्थ	P K	M D A	H Y U F	ट	छ ल ब म	च क म फ			
V Fifth पंचम	P R K	U E D M	L R	ल	य र प अ	ग न च प			
VI Six षष्ठम्	C Y	A L D M	P T G	ब ट च	ह क फ म	फ झ			

Scoring (मूल्यांकन) : (1) Mistake of Transposition/स्थान दोष =

(2) Mistake of Omission/चूक दोष =

(3) Mistake of Commission/युक्त दोष =

(4) Mistake of Transposition and Commission /स्थान दोष व युक्त दोष =

Remark : Two separate sets of 3 stimulant list each for two subjects are given in the above test.

टिप्पणी : उपर्युक्त परीक्षण-पत्र में दो प्रयोज्यों के लिए (हिन्दी अथवा अंग्रेजी किसी एक में करने के लिए तीन-तीन उद्दीपक-सूचियों के दो अलग-अलग सैट दिये गये हैं।

48/3 = 16

Part II : Auditory (श्रवणात्मक)

After saying 'Ready' and 'Start' to the subject, starting from first number of the table and then next successive number is told to and got repeated by the subject till the subject fails to repeat the number correctly.

प्रयोज्य को 'रैडी' व 'शुरू' संकेत के बाद तालिका की सूची की प्रथम संख्या से प्रारम्भ करते हुए क्रमशः सूची की अग्रिम एक-एक अधिक अंक वाली संख्या, उस समय तक सुनाई गई तथा साथ ही साथ प्रयोज्य से दुहरवा कर सुनी गई, जब तक कि वह सूची की किसी संख्या को सही रूप से दुहराने में असफल हो जाए।

List No.	Stimulating List	Response List	Span of Memory
सूची संख्या	उद्दीपक सूची	प्रत्युत्तर- सूची	मूल्यांकन
First प्रथम	8 2 7 5 1 8 2 7 9 5 8 2 8 6 9 5 4 1 3 8 5 2 6 7 3 4 9 1 5 8 2 1 6 9 2 8 6 3 7 5 1 4 3 9 8 2 7 4 1 6 3 5	8 2 7 5 1 8 2 7 9 5 8 2 8 6 9 5 4 1 3 8 5 2 6 7 3 X 4 9 1 5 8 2 1 6 ✓ 9 2 8 6 3 7 5 1 4 X 3 9 8 2 7 4 1 6 3 5 X	8
Second द्वितीय	5 6 1 8 5 2 7 3 4 9 1 6 6 6 5 8 4 7 2 5 9 7 4 1 8 7 2 8 5 3 6 4 1 4 9 5 7 1 3 6 2 8 8 1 7 4 9 2 5 9 2 6	5 6 1 ✓ 8 5 2 7 ✓ 3 4 9 1 6 ✓ 6 6 5 8 4 7 ✓ 2 5 9 7 4 1 8 ✓ 7 2 8 5 3 6 4 1 ✓ 4 9 5 7 1 3 6 2 8 ✓ 8 1 7 4 9 2 5 9 2 6 X	8
Third तृतीय	9 5 7 5 2 9 4 6 9 7 3 8 7 3 8 2 5 9 3 9 5 8 6 2 7 8 3 7 9 2 4 1 5 2 7 1 6 3 8 5 9 4 9 1 8 3 7 4 6 2 5 8	9 5 7 ✓ 5 2 9 4 ✓ 6 9 7 3 8 ✓ 7 3 8 2 5 9 ✓ 3 9 5 8 6 2 7 ✓ 8 3 7 9 2 4 1 5 X 2 7 1 6 3 8 5 9 4 X 9 1 8 3 7 4 6 2 5 8 X	7

contd..

$$2 \frac{2}{3} = 7.66$$

List No.	Stimulating List	Response List	Span of Memory
सूची संख्या	उद्दीपक सूची	प्रत्युत्तर- सूची	मूल्यांकन
Fourth चतुर्थ	8 5 9 6 9 4 2 7 1 9 4 8 9 2 2 5 1 7 4 7 2 8 3 1 9 3 8 5 2 7 4 1 3 5 2 8 9 3 6 4 7 1 2 9 6 5 3 4 8 1 7 3		
Fifth पंचम	9 5 8 2 9 4 7 6 9 4 1 5 7 1 9 4 3 9 9 1 3 8 2 7 4 8 2 6 9 1 7 3 5 5 1 4 8 6 3 7 2 9 1 9 2 5 7 4 8 3 6 2		
Six षष्ठम्	1 8 5 2 7 5 9 6 1 9 4 7 7 4 8 5 9 6 8 2 7 5 1 9 3 4 7 6 3 5 8 2 8 2 8 2 7 1 6 5 9 4 7 2 5 8 1 4 2 6 3 9		

Note : In the above table two sets of 3-3 lists are given for two subjects.

टिप्पणी : उपर्युक्त तालिका में दो प्रयोज्यों के लिए (प्रत्येक के लिए तीन-तीन सूचियों के) दो अलग-अलग सेट दिए गये हैं।

EXPERIMENT NO. : 4

Title : Vineland Social Maturity Scale.

Problem : To measure the social maturity of the participant.

Participant's details :

Name - KB

Age - 8

Date of testing - 21 - 03 - 2023

Address - Bongaigaon, Assam

Introduction :

The Vineland Social Maturity Scale was developed by the American Psychologist Edger Arnold Doll (1953). The test measures communication skills, general self help ability, locomotion skills, occupational skills, self-direction, self help eating, self help dressing,

Teacher's Signature

socializing skills. Later, the test was adapted by the Dr. J. Bharath Raj and since then been used in many parts of the country. In addition to providing measure of social age (SA) and Social Quotient (SQ), this scale also identifies a child's social deficits as well as social assets. The scale is intended for children between the age of 0 to 15. This measurement is also known an excellent tool for identifying mental retardation as well as superior intelligence. There are 89 items on the test, measuring 8- different aspects of social maturity

- 1) Communical skills (Com).
- 2) General self-help ability (SHG).
- 3) Locomotion skills (LOC).
- 4) Occupation skills (Occ).
- 5) Socialisation (SOC).
- 6) Self help Eating (SHE).
- 7) Self help dressing (SHD).
- 8) Self direction (SD).

Parents along with the children are required to respond, which ensures that the responses are marked accurately since parents are usually assumed to recall their child's development accurately.

Typically, the mother is asked for answers. The child sits next to her and gives clear or correct answers when the parent fails to do so.

In addition, the scale provides a measure of the social quotient as well as maturity age level for each domain, which improves the capability of identifying developmental lags and subsequent training.

Vineland Social Maturity Scale is an excellent clinical technique despite its limitations and it includes a variety of questionnaires and psychometrics.

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Materials required :

- (i) Vineland Social Maturity Scale.
- (ii) Pen, pencil, paper, etc.

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Procedure :

The experiment started with rapport formation wherein the subject was made comfortable. The subject being a child was accompanied by his or her mother. The subject's mother was explained about the scale, its purpose and was reated around to make the subject feel at comfort. For certain items on the scale, direct questions were asked to check, if the specific characteristics was present.

For each characteristics that was present, the subject was given a score of 1. After scoring all the characteristics, the total raw score was calculated by summing up all the scores.

This raw score was then converted to social age using the table in the manual. This was then used to find out the social quotient

using the formula -

$$S. Q = \frac{\text{Social Age}}{\text{Actual Age}} \times 100 \text{ or } I. Q = \frac{M.A. \times 100}{C.A.}$$

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The social quotient derived from this formula was then interpreted.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

The subject scored a total of 75, which converts to a social age 116 months or 9.6 years, finally converting to a social quotient, i.e.

$$S.Q = \frac{\text{Social Age}}{\text{Actual Age}} \times 100$$

$$S.Q = \frac{9.6}{8} \times 100 \text{ Redd.}$$

$$S.Q = 120.$$

~~Thus showing no signs of social problems.~~

VINELAND SOCIAL MATURITY SCALE
INDIAN ADAPTATION

Dr. J. BHARTH RAJ

NAME : _____ AGE : _____ CASE NO : _____
ADDRESS : _____ DATE OF TESTING : 21/03/23
SCORE : 75
SOCIAL AGE : 9.6 yrs
SOCIAL QUOTIENT : 128

AGE LEVEL 0 - I YEAR

- ✓ 1. Cries/Laugh
- ✓ 2. Balances head
- ✓ 3. Grasps object within reach
- ✓ 4. Reaches for familiar persons
- ✓ 5. Rolls over (unassisted)
- ✓ 6. Reaches for nearby objects
- ✓ 7. Occupies self unattended
- ✓ 8. Sits unsupported
- ✓ 9. Pulls self upright
- ✓ 10. Talks/Imitates sounds
- ✓ 11. Drinks from cup or glass assisted
- ✓ 12. Moves about on floor (creeping/crawling)
- ✓ 13. Grasps with thumb and finger
- ✓ 14. Demands personal attention
- ✓ 15. Stands alone
- ✓ 16. Does not drool
- ✓ 17. Follows simple instructions

AGE LEVEL I - II YEAR

- ✓ 18. Walks about room unattended
- ✓ 19. Marks with pencil or crayon
- ✓ 20. Masticates (chews) solid or semi-solid food
- ✓ 21. Removes shoes or sandals, pulls off socks

- ✓ 22. Transfers objects
- ✓ 23. Overcomes simple obstacles
- ✓ 24. Fetches or carries familiar objects
- ✓ 25. Drinks from cup or glass unassisted
- ✓ 26. Walks or uses go-cart for walking
- ✓ 27. Plays with own hands
- ✓ 28. Eats with own hands
- ✓ 29. Goes about house or yard
- ✓ 30. Discriminates edible substances from non-edibles
- ✓ 31. Uses names of familiar objects
- ✓ 32. Walks up-stairs unassisted
- ✓ 33. Unwraps sweets, chocolates
- ✓ 34. Talks in short sentences

AGE BEVEL II - III YEAR

- ✓ 35. Asks go to toilet
- ✓ 36. Initiates own play activities
- ✓ 37. Removes shirt or frock
- ✓ 38. Eats with spoon
- ✓ 39. Drinks (water) unassisted
- ✓ 40. Dries own hands
- ✓ 41. Avoids simple hazards
- ✓ 42. Puts on shirt or frock unassisted(need not button)
- ✓ 43. Can do paper folding
- ✓ 44. Relates experiences

AGE BEVEL III - IV YEAR

- ✓ 45. Walks downstairs, one step at a time
- ✓ 46. Plays co-operatively at Kindergarten level
- ✓ 47. Buttons shirt or frock
- ✓ 48. Helps at little household tasks
- ✓ 49. 'Performs' for others
- ✓ 50. Washes hands unaided

AGE BEVEL IV - V YEAR

- ✓ 51. Cares for self at toilet
- ✓ 52. Washes face unassisted
- ✓ 53. Goes about neighbourhood unattended
- ✓ 54. Dresses self except for tying or buttoning
- ✓ 55. Uses pencil or crayon for drawing
- ✓ 56. Plays competitive exercises, games

AGE BEVEL V - VI YEAR

- ✓ 57. Uses hoops, flies kites, rides tricycles
- ✓ 58. Prints (writes) simple words
- ✓ 59. Plays simple table games
- ✓ 60. Is trusted with money
- ✓ 61. Goes to school unattended

AGE BEVEL VI - VII YEAR

- ✓ 62. Mixes rice 'properly' unassisted
- ✓ 63. Uses pencil for writing
- ✓ 64. Bathes self assisted
- ✓ 65. Goes to bed unassisted

AGE LEVEL VII - VIII YEAR

- ✓ 66. Tells time to quarter hour
- ✓ 67. Helps himself during meals
- ✓ 68. Refuses to believe in magic and fairy tales
- ✓ 69. Participates in pre-adolescent play
- ✓ 70. Combs or brushes hair

AGE LEVEL VIII - IX YEAR

- 71. Uses tools or utensils
- 72. Does routine household tasks
- 73. Reads on own initiative
- 74. Bathes self unaided

AGE LEVEL IX - X YEAR

- 75. Cares for self at table (meals)
- 76. Makes minor purchases
- 77. Goes about home freely

AGE LEVEL X - XI YEAR

- 78. Writes occasional short letters to friends
- 79. Makes independent choice of shops
- 80. Does small remunerative work; makes articles
- 81. Answers ads; writes letters for information

AGE LEVEL XI - XII YEAR

- 82. Does simple creative work
- 83. Is left to care for self or others
- 84. Enjoys reading books, newspapers, magazines

AGE LEVEL XIII - XV YEAR

- 85. Plays difficult games
- 86. Exercises complete care of dress
- 87. Buys own clothing accessories
- 88. Engages in adolescent group activities
- 89. Performs responsible routine chores

EXPERIMENT No. : 5Title : Bhatia Battery of Performance Test.Problem : To measure participant's intelligence.Participant's details :

Name -

Age -

Sex -

Address -

Introduction :

David Wechsler defined intelligence as "the aggregate or global capacity of the individual to act purposefully, to think rationally and to deal effectively with his environment." Alfred Binet, the French Psychologist, derived modern intelligence test, believed that intelligence behaviour would be manifested in such mental activities as reasoning, imagination,

insight, judgement and adaptability. Some psychologists held the view that all the cognitive abilities (such as abstraction, learning and dealing with novelty) are the manifestation of a single underlying factor, called General Factor or 'g' factor and specific abilities such as artistic ability, linguistic ability, mathematical or spatial ability referred constitute specific factor or 's' factor.

Thus, we may define intelligence as,

1. The ability to behave adaptively.
2. The ability to function successfully within a particular environment.
3. Ability to learn new things quickly, to solve different kinds of problems.

Origin and Early Developments :

The first attempt to develop test of intellectual ability was made more than century ago by "Sir Francis Galton," a naturalist and a mathematician, in 1884.

Galton administered a battery of tests measuring variables like head size, reaction time, visual acuity, auditory threshold and memory for visual forms, on more than 9000 visitors at the London Exhibition. Galton found no difference in intelligence, between eminent scientists and ordinary people on the basis of head size. Also, reaction time has also not related to other measures of intelligence. James McKeen Cattell (1860-1944) has also made significant contributions to the measurement of individual differences.

Mental testing movement began with the development of the first intelligence test by Alfred Binet and another French psychologist "Theophile Simon" in 1905. The French government commissioned Binet to discover an objective method of assessing intellectual level of French school children. The major concern was to

identify children who were unable to profit from public school education.

The task for Binet and Simon was;

1. To devise a scale that would select children with intellectual disability.
2. Indicate the nature of special instruction that could benefit those children.
3. To improve the diagnosis of severely retarded institutionalized children, though it was the secondary objective.

Binet assumed intelligence could be measured by task that required reasoning and problem solving abilities. Binet published the first test in 1905 in collaboration with Simon and revised it 1908 and in 1911. The test was constructed with items of common information, word definitions, reasoning items and ingenuity. The measure of intelligence was mental age (MA). Binet and Simon assumed that intelligence grows with the child's

Chronological age (Actual Age). Thus, the child who passes all the items at the 7-year level is mentally 7-years of age irrespective of his or her Chronological age (Actual Age) or we can say the child is able to do the test items that 50 to 70% of 7-year old children can pass. In Binet's views, a slow or dull child is like a normal child whose mental growth is retarded. The slow child would perform on the level that is below his actual age whereas, the bright child can perform up to the level of children above his or her Chronological age or actual age. The items of Binet's scale are arranged in increasing level difficulty.

The higher a child could go on the scale in answering the item, the higher his or her mental age will be.

In 1916, Lewis Terman, published the Stanford version of Binet test, that is known as Stanford Binet Intelligence.

Scale. Terman adapted the test items developed by Binet for American school children. Stanford Binet Intelligence Scale (SBIS) was revised in 1937, 1960, 1972, 1986 and recently in 2003. Binet's concept of mental age was retained in SBIS. But Terman used intelligence quotient as an index of intelligence. The term IQ, from the German Intelligenz Quotient was suggested by the German psychologist "William Stern" (1912). Intelligence Quotient (IQ) expresses the relation of mental age (MA) to the real age (Chronological Age - CA).

$$IQ = \frac{MA}{CA} \times 100$$

IQ is calculated by dividing a child's mental age in months by his CA.

An average child of 7-years whose (M.A) is also 7-years, his IQ

$$\text{will be } \frac{84}{84} = 100$$

The number 100 is used as a multiplier to eliminate the decimals. So, the IQ of this child will be 100. IQ in intelligence tests now is no longer calculated using this equation.

Tables are used to convert raw scores on the test into standard scores, which express the IQ. 1986 version of the test uses percentiles to express the level of intelligence in a particular group. The 1986 revision of the Stanford - Binet is grouped into four broad areas: verbal reasoning, abstract / visual reasoning, quantitative reasoning and STM. Terman chose the category ranges for score levels on that test with standard deviation 16.

The scores are obtained by converting raw scores into standard scores.

Raw scores are the actual scores obtained on the test. These scores are converted by the tables which contain age appropriate standardized scores given in the manual.

It was felt that Stanford - Binet test depended heavily on linguistic ability. In 1939, David Wechsler developed a new test - Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale (WAIS). WAIS comprises of a verbal scale and a performance scale. These two yield separate scores and a full scale IQ. Later, similar tests were used by Wechsler for children, Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children - WISC (1958). The verbal scale in WAIS consists of information comprehension, arithmetic similarities, digit span, vocabulary and letter number sequencing.

The performance scale consists of digit symbol, picture completion, block design, picture arrangement, matrix reasoning, object assembly and symbol search. Both the Stanford and Wechsler scales show good reliability and validity and are widely used test to measure intelligence. Wechsler proposed different category ranges with a standard deviation of 15 by which IQ scores could be explained.

All the above tests were individual tests of intelligence, i.e. these tests may be administered on one person at a time. The wider social settings brought the need for such test that can be given to a large number of participants at a time. Group ability tests were devised for such purpose. Group ability tests may be administered to a large number of people by a single examiner and are usually pencil and paper test. Individual test focuses on global ability, their major purpose

being to assess a general trait. The focus of the group tests is to predict academic or occupational performance. Group tests of intelligence are more often used for initial screening in schools (Scholastic Assessment Test - SAT) and industries.

These tests may be followed by individual testing if more information is required. Individual tests are preferred by psychologists in clinics, hospitals and other settings where a clinical diagnosis is required.

About the test: At present, many I.Q. tests have been developed to suit the cultural milieu of an individual. There are also culture fair tests that are applicable to all the participants or persons irrespective of their culture. Culture-fair tests are free from any verbal content that measure culture specific and Test that you are required to administer is "Bhatia Battery of Performance Test".

"Bhatia's Battery of Performance" Test of intelligence was conducted by C.M. Bhatia in 1953. This test was developed for use on Indian Population. It includes the following five sub tests.

1. Koh's Block Design and Pass along Tests. (Test No. 1 and 2)

(i) Note the particulars of the subject as required in the Scoring sheet. Note also whether the subject is literate or illiterate. Illiterate is one who has not been to a school or has not stayed there long enough to acquire ordinary reading and writing.

(ii) Note the observations very carefully and faithfully. Record the times as carefully as you can with the help of a stop watch as far as possible. A friend may help you in recording the time.

(iii) Give the tests in a natural manner.

Obtain the confidence of the subject.

Talk in the subject's own dialect if possible. But stick to the procedure of the tests rigidly. Give only as much aid or hint to the subject as is permissible. When the subject fails, do not put on a very serious look. Keep cheerful business like attitude throughout.

(iv) Start testing with Koh's Block Design Test -

(1) Place four cubes before the subject. Explain how they are all alike and coloured in a particular way. Let him handle and examine the cubes at leisure and confidently and let him feel at home.

(2) Show him Card No. 1. Tell him that a design like this has to be prepared with the cubes. Even if he attempts to prepare the design himself, you should demonstrate the design

to every subject.

(3) Mix up the blocks. Now ask him to prepare design No. 1, as you have already shown him. Note the time.

(4) If the subject succeed in the above within the time limit, namely 2-minutes, proceed to Design No. 2 and ask him to construct it without demonstration or help from your side.

(5) Proceed in this manner with successive designs.

(6) When the subject fails in particular design within the time limit, demonstrate the design after he has failed. Do not discuss. Do not let him again try this design. Pass on to the next which of course, he must again try independently.

(7) When the subject comes to Design No. 6, give him five more blocks making the total nine, when he comes to design No. 8, give him the remaining seven, making total 16.

(8) Stop the test when failure has been recorded twice in succession.

(9) The time limit for Designs No.s 1-5 is 2 minutes each and for designs No.s 6-10 is 3 minutes.

(10) In the Remarks column you may note anything particular or peculiar you find about the subject in making the designs.

(V) In giving the Pass along Test:

(1) Take the first and the smallest box, and the card No. 1. Point out to the subject that the red block

has been placed near the blue end and the blue blocks near the red end. Explain that the red block must come to the end of the red side and the blue blocks to the blue side as in the card. Emphasize that blocks have not to be lifted, but may only be moved.

Demonstrate the solution of the first box to every subject.

(2) Again place the card No. 1 and the box and ask the subject to do as you have already just demonstrated. Record success or failure within the time limit.

(3) Proceed to Designs Nos. 2, 3, etc. with the appropriate boxes and after having placed the blocks properly in the initial position as required in the text. The initial position is obtained by simply reversing

the coloured ends of the box. The coloured ends of the box must however be finally placed before the subject as in the Design Card which must be presented to the subject with the number of the card up.

(4) When the subject fails in particular design within the time limit, demonstrate the design after he has failed. Do not discuss. Do not let him again try this design. Pass on to the next which, of course, he must again try independently.

(5) Stop the test, when failure has been recorded twice in succession.

(6) The time limit for Design 1-4 is 2 minutes each and for designs 5-8 is 3 minutes each.

(7) In the remarks column, you may note anything particular or peculiar you find about the subject in solving the designs.

Pattern - Drawing (Test No. 3)

1) There are 8 patterns of increasing difficulty from 1st to 8th.

2) Give the following instruction to the subject

Here is paper and pencil - I shall show a figure to you, Place a card before the subject - Let the card be so displayed that the number of the card appears the top before the subject.

Now, make the figure like this without repeating your lines and without lifting your pencil when once you have started drawing. The card should remain in full view of the subject throughout.

3) Let the subject try successive patterns, stop when failure is recorded twice in succession.

4) Provide a plain white sheet of paper to the subject on which to draw the patterns, successive patterns may be drawn on the same sheet as long as there is room. Put the name of the subject at the top of the corner.

5) Allow a maximum of 9 minutes for each of the first four patterns. Allow a maximum of 3 minutes for patterns No. 5 to 8. The subject may take as many attempts on the paper as he likes within the time limit.

6) Demonstrate the first pattern, if necessary. It is only meant to give the subject confidence and facility in drawing.

7) When a failure occurs in one of the patterns, demonstrate this, but do not let the subject try this

pattern again. Pass on this next, stop when failure is recorded in two successive designs.

8) Watch the subject while he is drawing. If he repeats a line or lifts his pencil, remind him of the conditions. Ask him to commence after proper thought if he makes a drawing wrong, cross it out and ask him to start afresh. Encourage him to try as many times he likes within the time limit. Before you record a failure in a particular pattern.

9) The solutions are given at the back of the cards. Try out the pattern yourself first. You will be able to see the device. Solutions other than those given are also possible and should be familiar to you.

Immediate Memory for Sounds (a) Direct (Test No. 4)

- 1) Immediate memory too has a close relation with mental development or general intelligence.
- 2) English consonants have been taken as the units of sounds, because they put the literate and the illiterate at par.
- 3) Give the instructions to the subject:
I will say something. Listen attentively
Repeat it after I have finished.
"Listen".
- 4) We start the two letters (or sounds).
This is merely to give practice to the subject. Read out distinctly and with even intonation. Proceed with more letters till failure is recorded. Under each head we have given three alternative sets of letters failure is recorded in the first set, try the second and third alternative

sets. If failure is recorded in all the three alternatives a final failure is recorded and we stop. We do not proceed up the series any more.

Immediate Memory for Sounds (b) Reversed (Test No. 4)

1) The instructions in this part are: "Whatever I say, you must say backwards. If I say 'ka cha', you say 'cha ka'."

Explain this reversal process clearly to the subject if necessary using another set of two syllables as a second example.

2) Proceed up the series till the failure is recorded. Failure means a failure in all the three alternatives of particular set.

Picture Construction Test.
(Test No. 5)

Instructions are as follows :

- 1) This is the fifth and the last test of battery.
- 2) This is a comparatively easy test for the age group of 11 to 16 years and has been purposely put in to enable some of the inferior children to score appreciably.
- 3) The test consists of 5 graded sub-tests.
- 4) The general instructions will be :

Here are number of pieces (specify 2, 4, 6, 8, 12 as the case may be) of a picture. Put the pieces together to form a picture.

- 5) Start with the first sub-test. Most

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of the children will be able to do this themselves without your aid. In any case demonstrated and explain clearly what is to be done. This first sub-test is only to give practice and to let the subject understand clearly what is wanted of him.

6) Pass on then to the second (picture divided into 4 parts), 3rd (picture divided into 6 parts), 4th (picture divided into 8 parts), and 5th, the last (picture divided into 12 parts).

7) Follow usual procedure i.e.,

a) If failure occurs in a sub-test, demonstrate and then pass on to the next.

b) Stop with two successive failures.

8) If the subject is able to pass the first three sub-tests, then in the

fourth and fifth sub-tests, in case of failures, record not only failure but the number of pieces the subject was able to fit in correctly within the time limit, i.e., for example 6 out of 8 or 7 out of 8, in the case of 4th sub-test and 6 out of 12 or 9 out of 12 etc, in the case of the 5th sub-test.

9) The time limit is 2 minutes each for sub-tests 1 to 3 and 3 minutes each for sub-tests Nos. 4 and 5. Record both the time taken by the subject and failure or success.

10) The pieces of a sub-test must be presented before the child in a pile in a serial order that has been made at the back of the places. Of course the picture sides of the pieces will be exposed to the child. The numbers at the back are only to guide the examiner in placing the

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pieces in the desired standard order initially before the child.

The above has two expectations. In this, sub-test No. 1, put the two pieces side by side. In sub-test 5 put the pieces in two piles. In one pile put pieces 1 to 6 and in the second, by its side pieces 7 to 12. Pieces 1 and 7 will thus appear before the subject on top side by side to give him the initial correct start.

1) You can find out the solutions of the sub-tests easily yourself, but they are given below to make you perfectly sure about them. Make yourself familiar with the solution before you give the test.

Solution : Sub-test 2	
1	2
4	3

Solution : sub-test 3		
4	1	3
6	5	2

Solution : sub-test 4	
7	5
4	8
3	1
6	2

Solution : sub-test 5		
12	9	6
2	5	3
1	7	8
4	10	11

Scoring : The scoring standards for the various tests are as under :

Both time and success are to be taken into account. The Scoring Standards have been kept as uniform and simple as possible.

Koh's : For the first five designs and for each design.

- (i) 2 - marks for success within a minute.
- (ii) 1 - mark for success between 1 minute and 2 minutes.
- (iii) 0 - mark for a failure or success after the time limit.

For designs Nos. 6 to 10 and for each design.

- (i) 3 - marks for success within a minute,
- (ii) 2 - marks for success between 1 minute and 2 minutes (but excluding 2 minutes),
- (iii) 1 - mark for success between 2 and 3 minutes.

(iv) 0 - mark for a failure, or success after the time limit.

Maximum possible score : 25

Pass along : for the first four sub-tests and for each sub-test.

(i) 2 - marks for success within a minute.

(ii) 1 - marks for success between 1 minute and 2 minutes.

(iii) 0 - mark for a failure or success after the time limit.

For the last four sub-tests and for each sub-test.

(i) 3 - marks for success within a minute.

(ii) 2 - marks for success between 1 minute and 2 minute and 2 minute - excluding.

(iii) 1 - mark for success between 2 and 3 minutes.

(iv) 0 - mark for a failure or success after the time limit.

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Maximum possible score : 20.

Patterns : Exactly the same as for the
Pass along Text.

Maximum possible score : 20

Memory : Direct : One mark each
for the number of digits or sound
in the maximum correct reproduction.

Maximum possible score provided for 9.

Reverse : One mark each for the
number of digits or sound in the
maximum correct reversed reproduction.

Maximum possible score provided : 6

Pictures 1 to 3 : Pictures 1 to 3 and for each of them.

- (i) 2 - marks for success within a minute.
- (ii) 1 - mark for success between 1 minute and 2 minutes.
- (iii) 0 - mark for a failure or success after the time limit.

Pictures 4 and 5 and for each of them.

- (i) 3 - marks for success within a minute.
- (ii) 2 - marks for success between 1 minute and 2 minute (but excluding 2 minutes).
- (iii) 1 - mark for success between 2 and 3 minutes.
- (iv) 0 - mark for failure or success after the time limit.

~~For Picture 4 and 5, however credit in addition to that earned according~~

to the above schedule, is to be given as under :

For Picture 4 : 1 mark, provided that at least 6 of the 8 parts have been correctly put within the time limit.

For Picture 5 : 2 marks provided that at least 9 of the 12 parts have been correctly put together and 1 - mark provided that at least 6 of the 12 parts have been correctly put together, both within the time limit.

Maximum possible score : 15

Maximum possible score for the whole Bhatta's Battery : 95

Time : The total time taken in the administration of the battery to a single individual is rather less than an hour.

Approved
26/3/27

Teacher's Signature

An **exercise book**, also called **version book** that is used to copy down schoolwork and notes. A student will usually have a different exercise book for each separate subject. The exercise book format is different for some subjects - for the majority of subjects, the exercise book will contain ruled pages, but for other subjects such as Mathematics, the exercise book will be blank or will be lined to aid in the drawing of graphs, tables or other diagrams. The rapid expansion of paper production was truly enhanced by the invention of the printing press in the 15th century. Over the years quality of paper has continued to improve which has enabled Oxford Paper Products to use the highest quality of paper available, to manufacture exercise books.

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